

Shared Space in Public Real Estate through Service Design

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INTRODUCTION

Danish municipalities' economy is under economical pressure, and at the same time a lot of the municipalities have a challenge with public real estate, which is not used in an efficient manner. These years, the Danish society focuses a lot on sustainability, which is reflected in the strategies and policies the municipalities run with. Many municipalities have never had a strategy for public real estate, and now that they are forced to address the issue due to economical pressure and sustainable goals, a lot of the municipalities do not have a method for addressing the issue.

METHOD

The project has followed a pilot project in Lundtofte to study an example on how shared space can be implemented in public estate to optimize the use of public real estate. Lundtofte is a part of Lyngby-Taarbæk municipality in Denmark north from Copenhagen, and the pilot project looked at nine buildings and 12.660 m² including a school at 7.120 m². During the project the municipality focused on public participation which they got a positive response on. The case study was analysed as a service design method with the four steps: 1. Observe and listen, 2. Develop scenarios, 3. Testing the new service, 4. Design briefing.

RESULTS

The project in Lundtofte ended with a scenario, where up to five of the public buildings were to be sold and the municipality would then have a decrease of square meters in Lundtofte by up to 24 %.

CONCLUSION

The case study shows service design can be used for improving a service offered by a municipality within facilities management. The project end up presenting seven focus areas which will give a successful process for a municipality, which wish to use shares space in public real estate.

1. Strategy for public real estate in the municipality
2. The motivation for using shared space
3. What to share and how to share
4. The level of service – general or tailor-made
5. How to involve the citizens
6. Keep the public involved and informed throughout the length of the project
7. Observe and listen, scenarios, test and design briefing

By using service design and following the seven focus areas, which uses shared space in public real estate, the use of the real estate will be optimized, thus the amount of estate can be decreased which will reflect in a decrease in the energy consumption and operational costs. Furthermore, shared space can support social responsibility by letting different groups of the society interact. It will result in an improved service which supports public participation in society and all together it will support the sustainable development in the municipality.